

AROUND THE CAMPFIRE - RESILIENCE AND INTELLIGENCE

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AROUND THE CAMPFIRE - RESILIENCE AND INTELLIGENCE

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Proceedings Series

Cumulus Association of
universities and Colleges
of Art, Design and Media

Rovaniemi 2019

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Empathy for resilience

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Abstract

The essay stresses the potential value of empathy in designing strategies for resilience. We question the traditional idea of empathy as an individual skill addressed to understand the other, in support of a conceptualization closer to the phenomenological interpretation, focused on the relational dynamics at stake in human encounters. The paper reconsiders empathy as an experience valuable for strengthening a resilient attitude within collaborative projects. A case study will be featured, i.e. *Design in The Middle*, an ongoing project that gathers designers, architects and social activists from the Middle East/Euro-Med regions with the aim of generating design proposals to address challenges relevant to the Middle East. As participants come from very different cultural, political and religious backgrounds, their cooperation is a central and critical issue, which might benefit from contextual and relational “rules” enabling empathic experiences. In the context of the first *Design in The Middle* workshop (2017), some strategies have proven to be crucial in enabling effective communication over complex design issues. These strategies will be analysed according to a methodology developed in a previous research carried out by the author(s) (Devecchi, 2018) about the role of empathy in collaborative processes. Assuming that a resilient society preserves and supports cultural diversity, *Design in the Middle* stands as an example of collaborative design practice aimed at creating a more resilient future for these regions in which the coexistence of diverse cultural, religious and political positions is a substantial matter of concern.

Author keywords

Empathy; collaborative practices; social resilience; design methodologies.

Introduction

“Even twins have different fingerprints”, states one of the participants in *Design in the Middle #01 Workshop* when asked to relate his/her experience of the project to empathy (Interview by the author, May-June 2017). He or she – the survey was anonymised – believes that the multiplicity of cultural, social, religious backgrounds brought by the attendees – in other words, their diversity – added value to the experience and to the project’s outcomes, since it was a basic condition for empathy to flow. *Design in the Middle* is an ongoing project involving designers, who live or come from the Middle East/Euro-Med region, in co-imagining new “forms of governance, coexistence, ownership and alliances” [Designinthemiddle.org]. In this essay, we discuss the project as an example of collaborative practice aimed at building more resilient behaviours by increasing the empathic experience among participants.

Research stresses the potential of cultural activities engaging people in collaborative practices focused on weaving or re-sewing a fragile social fabric and thus enhancing social resilience (Arvanitakis, 2014; Manzini & Thorpe, 2018; Manzini & Till, 2015; Meroni, 2008). Moreover, scholars have underlined the role of empathy in promoting cooperation (Devecchi, 2018; Mattelmäki, 2018; Sennett, 2012). Therefore, the three threads of empathy, cooperation and resilience seem to be somehow interwoven. This study aims at unravelling the relation between them, as relevant to the design discourse, and follows a prior research on the concept of empathy, its complexity as a relational human experience, and its crucial role in collaborative design processes (Devecchi & Guerrini, 2017; Devecchi, 2018). Far from being exhaustively depicted as a social skill allowing one to identify with someone else, share his/her concerns and take his/her perspective, empathy has more to do with acknowledging the irreducible differences characterising each one of us and the way we deal with diversity. According to recent studies on phenomenology and ethics (Boella, 2018a, 2018b; Zahavi, 2014), the lived experience of empathy contributes to including the existence of the other in one’s own personal horizon. The acknowledgment of otherness and “unlikeliness” (Eggebert, 2018) lays the foundation for meaningful relationships. Dealing with different and not-previously-known cultural identities may be highly challenging. It requires the capacity of negotiating and reshaping our own identity within each encounter. Collaborative design processes play a crucial role in rehearsing this continuous negotiation, opening ourselves to change and adaptation. In this respect, collaborative design practices may contribute to building cultural resilience, basically the ability of adapting our sense of self when challenged by the other breaking in.

The challenging nature of resilience

In the last decades, resilience has proven to be a highly multidisciplinary concept suitable to the tasks of many scientific fields dealing, from different perspectives, with risks analysis, such as urban and rural ecology, social engineering, developmental psychology, micro- and macro-economy, organizational management, and policy making (Ponis & Koronis, 2012; Wilson & Arvanitakis, 2013). The scrutiny of the huge amount of literature available on

the subject largely exceeds the task of this short essay. However, tracing the path back to the origin of the notion of resilience, and focusing on some key-concepts, may help understanding the reasons of such a success.

In the domain of Material Science, where it first appears, resilience is the power of a material of resuming an original shape after a stress such as compression, bending etc. Mechanics can measure this power as the energy per volume absorbed by a material when it is subjected to strain (OED, 2010). In other words, (mechanical) resilience is the capacity of "bouncing back", after strain.

In the 1970s, the concept became part of the behavioural scientists' vocabulary. Psychologists, in particular, defined as resilience the positive adaptation within a context of significant adversity. The notion originally focused on the individual capabilities – in early studies, Werner and Smith (1977) talked about "vulnerable but invincible" children, who thrive despite high-risk status: parental mental illness, maltreatment, poverty and community violence (Garmezy, 1974; Werner, Bierman & French, 1971). After substantial scrutiny and discussion, (psychological) resilience has progressively grown in complexity, and now refers to a dynamic process mutually involving the subject and the context (Luthar, Cicchetti & Becker, 2000).

Similarly, in Ecology, early definitions of resilience focused on the "ability to absorb change and disturbance and still maintain the same relationships between populations and state variables" (Holling, 1973, p.14). In this disciplinary context, too, resilience can be measured by calculating the magnitude of disturbance that a system could tolerate and still move forward (Carpenter et al., 2001). Further studies lead to a more comprehensive definition of (ecological) resilience, which stresses the interactive and dynamic nature of phenomena involved. In this new perspective, "resilience is the capacity of a system to absorb disturbance and reorganize while undergoing change so as to still retain essentially the same function, structure, identity, and feedback" (Walker, Holling, Carpenter & Kinzig, 2004, p.5).

In extending its fields of application, resilience also changed in nature. From a Political Science perspective, David Chandler (2014) makes a distinction between "classical" and "post-classical" resilience, which may be useful for understanding this transformation. "The intimate logical roots of classical understandings of resilience are framed in terms of the inner resources and capacities of the autonomous individual". There is "a strong subject/object divide", between the subject's internal capacity and the "pressures or stresses [that are] understood to be externally generated" (Chandler, 2014, p.6). In this respect, resilience is implicitly linked to the classical modern thinking. Whereas, in the post-classical framing, resilience becomes "an emergent and adaptive process of subject/object interrelations", as it deals more and more with dynamic and nonlinear systems. "We increasingly understand adaptation to the world as being inseparable from the world in which we adapt" (Chandler, 2014, p.7).

Therefore, subject and context are interwoven, and resilience is not merely a matter of adaptation of the former to the latter, rather, it delineates a mutual interchange. The way we read this interchange affects the way we address

resilience-related phenomena. In the domain of Social Geography, Keck and Sakdapolrak (2013) delve in this direction. After substantial analytical work, they focus on the principles underlying the concept of resilience, which, according to their interpretation, “can be defined [...] as a system’s capacity to *persist* in its current state of functioning while facing disturbance and change, to *adapt* to future challenges, and to *transform* in ways that enhance its functioning [italics in the text]” (Keck & Sakdapolrak, 2013, p.8). These features – particularly the last one (transformation) – help the authors reshape the meaning of resilience in social contexts (social resilience), a fundamental point of view for the purposes of this essay, as it adopts an “actor-oriented perspective”, that is, a reading of resilience as a tool for fostering collaborative social transformation practices.

Keck and Sakdapolrak acknowledge that social resilience is still “a concept in the making”, and its effectiveness accordingly requires further scrutiny. However, a trajectory can be traced: “from its initial meaning, referring simply to actors’ capacity to respond, [it has] enlarged to encompass actors’ capacity to learn and adapt; [and] now the concept also includes their capacity to participate in governance processes and to transform societal structures themselves” (Keck & Sakdapolrak, 2013, p.13).

This short inquiry on the notion of resilience provides us with some hints. Progressively, problems addressed have enlarged in scale and changed in nature: from molecular mechanisms to individual behaviours to environmental and societal interactions. In all these contexts, resilience has proven to be a vital conceptual tool for augmenting the understanding of the material world, of human beings, of communities and the environment, for it is strongly linked with two fundamental contemporary conditions: risk and change (Beck, 1992; Walker & Salt, 2006). These crucial issues, we cannot expand on within this essay, lay, however, in the background as key-components framing the concept of resilience. In fact, the notion itself increases its relevance in parallel to the growing concern with societal risks and social-ecological systems change – the “adversities”, we may say. The focus shifts from subject-oriented to subject/context-oriented, and the relationship between the two evolves accordingly: from adapting to steady conditions to interacting with dynamic ones.

This trajectory, however, is under dispute. There is a large consensus among scholars about the systemic nature of most resilience-related problems. More questionable is whether resilience contributes to solve them by adaptation or by transformation. In this respect, the concept proves to be a litmus test between those who prioritize the external – or context-related – factors of change and those who champion an active role of both individuals and communities in facing them. In this respect, the issue of *how* to enhance resilience is crucial.

For the purpose of this essay we adopt a collaborative perspective such as the one embedded in the concept of social resilience, assuming that cooperation can act as a bridge between the two parallel goals of enhancing the resilience of and promoting empathy among individuals and communities.

The lived experience of empathy

In recent years, empathy has become an “umbrella term covering a number of different experiences” (Boella, 2018b, p.2), its meaning remains superficial as long as summarised in the popular metaphor of *putting yourself in someone else’s shoes*. Significantly, as for the word itself, the philosopher Laura Boella claims the need to switch from the singular to the plural form. *Empathies*, in her view, more correctly captures this multifaceted phenomenon dealing with complex stratified experiences that occur when individuals have any encounter whatsoever (Boella, 2018a).

Shortcomings of the conceptualization of empathy exist in all fields, including the design discourse. Design researchers and practitioners recently began to perceive the inadequacy of the traditional empathic design approach, developed for a designer-user-product/service relation that substantially changed over time (Devecchi, 2018; Mattelmäki, 2018; Battarbee et al., 2014; Cipolla & Bartolo, 2014; Manzini & Till, 2015; Mattelmäki et al., 2014; Sustar & Mattelmäki, 2017). Especially in the emerging collaborative approach to design, the role of human relationship is acknowledged as crucial. Since co-design has gained momentum, designers are no longer asked to merely understand their users; rather, they are themselves involved in a process in which everyone – expert or non-expert – plays a role in achieving a common goal (Sanders & Stappers, 2008; Manzini, 2015). Empathy as a skill, even though acquired with specific techniques, ultimately falls short of the demand for establishing a truly dialogic exchange aimed at encouraging cooperation among multiple actors (Meroni & Sangiorgi, 2011; Cipolla & Manzini, 2009).

The discourse on empathy has recently taken two main directions: on the one hand, the neuroscientific research about the *mirror neurons system* as the bio-physiological root of the empathic behaviour (Gallese, 2001; Gallagher, 2012); on the other, the re-emergence and revision of the phenomenological heritage on empathy dating back to Edmund Husserl, Max Scheler and Edith Stein by scholars like Dan Zahavi (2014) and Laura Boella (2018a, 2018b). The latter direction is relevant to our argument, since it explores the experiential dimension of the empathic act as a phenomenon occurring in the context of relational encounters. From this perspective, empathy becomes a phenomenon involving subjects experiencing each other, rather than a feeling, an emotion, or – more importantly – a skill of understanding the other via identification. Zahavi argues that empathy is a kind of “knowledge by acquaintance” (2014, p.151), for others are identified as irreducibly others, and acknowledged in their own terms. Consequently, the empathic act, intentional and immediate, discloses the existence of the other in our personal horizon, independently from any attribution of feeling, thought or desire driving his/her comprehension. In other words, empathy’s “primary focus is not what we have in common with others, but how we experience the existence of others who are different from us” (Boella, 2018b, p.5). Such a tenet “allows us to exclude a notion of empathy as an individual mental or affective state, in order to insist on its nature as a phenomenon that depends on the relations between two subjects and their specific contents” (Boella, 2018b, p.7). Key to this perspective is the concept of interdependence between humans, for we are mutually involved in building knowledge of ourselves and of the world around us.

Empathic experience, collaborative practices and resilience

With regard to design, the perspective on empathy explained above substantially puts aside the techniques for empathising that help designers know better who they are designing for, such as design probes, personas, role playing, etc. These empathic design methods achieve full efficacy as long as designers play a demiurgic role, in a process relying on the way he/she individually relates to users. Assuming that design practices bring people together through cooperation and co-designing (Gunn & Donovan 2012; Manzini, 2015), the relationships at stake involve all participants, designers included. In this context, empathic design tools should support strategies for enabling a kind of relational experience that – capitalising on diversity rather than commonalities – promotes a dialogic exchange among individuals. Richard Sennett (2012) argues that empathy relates to dialogic exchanges, since it – differently from sympathy that conveys identification – opens up to differences and discloses curiosity about people for who they are, on their own terms, forcing us to focus beyond ourselves. The term dialogic, unlike dialectic, concerns “a discussion which does not resolve itself by finding common ground. Though no shared agreements may be reached, through the process of exchange people may become aware of their own views and expand their understanding of one another” (Sennett, 2012, p.19). Assuming that empathy supports dialogic skills by bringing mutual knowledge about, and that dialogic skills lay the groundwork for cooperation, enabling empathic experiences may contribute to enabling collaboration.

Developing *enabling solutions and systems* (Manzini, 2015) is a fundamental issue in the broad discourse of design for social change, particularly when dealing with *creative communities* (Meroni, 2011) engaged in collaborative activities. Within this context, the project Cultures of Resilience (CoR), held at the University of the Arts London (UAL) between 2014 and 2016, featured a set of art and design research actions “weaving people and places”, with the aim of building socially resilient communities. Participatory art and design activities carried out within the framework of the CoR project have been created as opportunities for collaborative encounters between people who would not normally meet, so to establish new unforeseen relationships. In this respect, cooperating towards a common goal in a context that encourages dialogue, embodied engagement and meaningful relationships, contributes to build *communities-in-place*. “Social resilience requires the existence of groups of people who interact and collaborate in a physical context. Proximity and relationship with a place are what enable these people to self-organize and solve problems in a crisis” (Manzini & Thorpe, 2018, p.1). From this viewpoint, collaborative art and design processes provide the context for questioning our own identity and developing self-awareness through the exploration of atypical relationships. By testing our capacity of adapting to and negotiating with diversity, we can respond better to “discrepancy and dissemblance” (Rancière, 2009, p.7) generated by the unexpected encounter with the “unlikelihood of us” (Eggebert, 2018). Carla Cipolla (2018) stresses the need to intentionally enable vulnerability in collaborative practices. In her view, vulnerability is deeply connected to meaningful relationships for they must rely upon mutual exposure to one another’s presence. Being vulnerable means being open to the risk of meeting unknown persons and being able to establish with them a dialogue that reshapes your own identity.

Therefore, risk and change are inherent to resilience, also when it involves cultural identity and social relations. Collaborative practices prove to be effective ways to test resilient behaviours. Together with vulnerability, the lived experience of empathy push and nurture dialogic exchange and meaningful encounters, where differences are a value asset. Dialogues and relationships *per se*, of course, cannot be designed. However, both vulnerability and empathy can be enabled by “conceiving, assembling, and enhancing dedicated sets of actors, assets and artefacts” (Manzini & Thorpe, 2018, p.8) and by setting out favourable contextual conditions.

Design in the Middle. Where empathy, collaboration and resilience meet

In March 2017, 30 designers and architects from the Middle East/Euro-Med region gathered at the National Museum for the XXI Century Arts in Rome (MAXXI). They were invited to participate in the #01 Workshop of *Design in the Middle*, an ongoing project aimed at co-designing possible responses to challenging issues relevant to the Middle East, such as borders, religious diversity, migration, water and food resources, information mobility and cultural exchange (Perez & Tarazi, 2017). The project was curated by Maria Alicata, Merav Perez and Ezri Tarazi, and supported by Baruchello and Mondo Digitale Foundations. Participants had never met before, and had different links to the Middle East. Someone had fled years ago, someone had just left for studying or working, someone else still lived there. Clustered in five transdisciplinary groups, they worked around distinct – yet connected – critical topics for one week: *Nomadentity*, focused on challenges related to immigration, open borders, self-dignity and identity; *Core.ligious*, dealt with freedom of belief, awareness of personal spiritualism and faith; *Lost in translation* explored communication, cultural exchanges and e-learning; *Digital dunes* was about data harvesting, mining and ensuring; *Food print* delved into water and food rights and resources, new agriculture and new energy supplies. “The goals of the workshop were multiple: to ignite and rehabilitate the fragile civic imagination of participants through the conception of alternative near-future scenarios, while eliciting a wide range of design proposals, from the imaginary to the applicable” (Perez & Tarazi, 2017, p.54308).

The Guido Reni room, usually a conference room, has been temporary unsettled for the purpose of the workshop. It was divided into two areas: a “pop up studio” equipped with tall yellow elements on wheels that created intimate working corners, and a public space for discussion and presentation. In this environment, especially conceived for encouraging dialogue and discussion, in smaller and larger groups alternatively, participants met after a month of preparatory work supported by a collaborative online platform. In Rome, they worked in teams achieving multiple results that were discussed within an open studio event with a panel including scholars and practitioners engaged in the issues at stake in the workshop. Curators claimed success for the initiative and considered it a highly meaningful opportunity for thinking and imagining beyond borders.

Three main reasons suggest an investigation into the case study of *Design in the Middle*: the workshop promotes a collaborative design practice; it elicits empathic experiences among participants, making room for meaningful dialogic encounters; it effectively builds social resilience in a conflict area. In this

respect, we may say that the workshop encompasses the three threads of cooperation, empathy and resilience, showing their reciprocity. Looking closer into the case study, we can recognize a number of *enablers* that contributed to the successful outcome of the project. Drawing upon a campaign of interviews with some of the participants run by the author(s) between May and June 2017, we can assess the efficacy of the *enablers* in achieving empathy, fostering collaboration and – ultimately – building resilience. The list of *enablers* takes up some of the insights of the CoR project, and partially overlaps with author(s)' previous studies (Devecchi, 2018; Devecchi & Guerrini, 2017). The latter achieved the identification of 4 contextual and 5 relational *enablers* of the empathic experience by investigating six case studies of participatory art practices. A contextual enabler pinpoints "an external condition, independent from participants' attendance at the event, installation, workshop or activity. It relates to the general circumstances set up to characterise the space and the time for the event to happen. [...] By relational enabler we mean a condition determined by making people involved interact in a particular way. Relational enablers concern the rules of interaction set up in the context of each case" (Devecchi, 2018, p.117-122). The research came out with merging the 9 *enablers* into a set of guidelines for designing the empathic experience in collaborative contexts.

As regards *Design in the Middle*, we must say that not all the *enabling strategies* featured below have been consciously designed by the organisers, although particular attention has been paid to the workshop setting.

- *Design in the Middle* has been hosted in a museum, an institution that, by its very nature, preserves cultural identity. Curators considered MAXXI appropriate for gathering people from different conflict areas, as it was an extra-territorial place, neutral and safe. Participants particularly appreciated working inside a museum in Italy, a place rich in history and culture they felt as a kind of "de-risked" environment (Interview by the author, May-June 2017). This enabling condition matches the author(s)' guideline *Safe Zone*, which suggests choosing locations "that conveys neutrality, safeness and freedom of thought" (Devecchi, 2018, p.153).
- The Guido Reni room was temporarily changed into a cosy studio environment, where it was easy to switch from small group work to shared dialogue and discussion. The tall yellow elements on wheels provided a dynamic and informal context that conveyed an open-minded attitude. With regard to the CoR project, Manzini and Thorpe (2018) claim the importance of triggering artifacts for enabling meaningful encounters. We may interpret these yellow elements "that referenced desert tents" (Perez & Tarazi, 2017, p. S4315) as triggering artefacts.
- The list of participants was drawn up accurately. The final group included "junior and seniors designers and architects from all over the Middle East/Euro-Med Region, students and designers from the Middle East who were studying or working in Europe, and a few European social designers and entrepreneurs who were actively involved with the issues at stake" (Perez & Tarazi, 2017, p.S4314). The resulting blend of perspectives, due to different

background, degree of education, life experiences, age and – especially – religious beliefs, could be potentially explosive. On the contrary, the workshop offered the opportunity for each and every voice to speak, building on diversity its most valuable outcomes. Equally concerned for their own countries, plagued by everlasting conflicts, participants discovered that their differences in opinion, expressed in a neutral context, could be a resource instead of a hindrance. Most of them referred to this specific experience as empathic (Interview by the author, May-June 2017). The choice of participants is an important issue also in the author(s)' research (Devecchi, 2018). The guideline *Embracing diversity* suggests we should select or cluster participants focusing on their differences (personal, cultural, professional) so to bring competition into collaborative processes.

- Organisers intentionally provided participants with little instructions. They considered that a detailed formulation was detrimental. As the task of the groups was itself to generate new design proposals, giving demanding briefs and setting key targets was inappropriate. Moreover, the titles of the clusters were attentively crafted to leave room for interpretation and critical thinking. The selected keywords (*Nomadentity, Lost in translation, Core.ligious, Food Print, Digital Dunes*) could provoke debate, and encourage the exploration of alternative perspectives with no specific outcome in mind. In this respect, participants were invited to stay “alert to the revelation of the unexpected” (Eggebert, 2018, p.13).
- Informal discussions, light encounters, opportunities for sitting all together and sharing personal life experiences were scheduled in the agenda of the workshop. The balance between highly demanding work and disengaged moments of exchange proved to be effective in building a cooperative attitude (Interview by the author, May-June 2017). Author(s)' corresponding guideline is *Never mind the clock*, which suggests how to plan a flexible schedule for collaborative activities (Devecchi, 2018).
- Perez and Tarazi reported that “most of the groups did not speak or think in terms of solving problems or developing objects. Rather, they focused on developing wide-ranging projects that tackle complex topics in a multi-dimensional approach” (2017, p.S4316). This recalls an observation by Manzini and Thorpe in the context of the CoR project about redundancy. They argue that many of the activities “appear to some extent superfluous – offering a positive redundancy – and hence capable of enabling participants to prototype and practice, to rehearse new ways of being together that may be drawn upon in future, more crucial contexts.” (2018, p.7-8).
- Not all the strategies set up for the workshop were successful. Significantly, web-based activities proved to be mostly ineffective. One month before the workshop took place, a preparatory online session was launched, in order to provide a knowledge base for all participants. Compared to the energy, enthusiasm and success of the in-place activity, the remote preparatory work “did not prove itself as an effective collaborative tool” (Perez & Tarazi, 2017,

p.S4316). This failure confirms that collaborative practices are not suitable for the Internet, as they do not provide participants with the necessary environmental conditions for enhancing empathic experience. To use Sennett’s words about online collaboration, “in undertaking cooperation, users are capable of handling more complexity than the programmers provided for” (Sennett, 2012, p.29). Until we learn how to teach computers to behave empathically – or we might say, unless we do – empathy will remain a human behaviour. In this respect, empathy works as an antidote to the Internet.

Conclusion

Design in the Middle provides some hints on the dynamic connection between three components of collaborative practices: space, people and activities. An accurate fine-tuning of the three aspects can enhance the transformative potential of a process and contribute to successful outcomes.

As regards space, we can say that collaborative practices are usually in-place activities (Manzini & Thorpe, 2018); designers and experts not always live in the place – more frequently come from elsewhere – and residents act as hosts. This situation may help conversations or not, depending on the conditions established among participants. However, a peer-to-peer cooperation can start between residents and experts as the former bring a first-hand knowledge of local problems and the latter the methodologies and skills required to cope with them. *Design in the Middle* provides participants with an extra-territorial space, a neutral, out-of-context environment where differences or hierarchies of any kind (personal, cultural, professional) – whether established or not – do not depend on the place. As in an in-vitro experiment, participants can focus on the issues at stake without any distraction – or inspiration – from a specific context. This reflection corroborates author(s)’ *Safe zone* guideline (Devecchi, 2018), which in turn recalls the concept of “de-risked” environment crucial to CoR activities (Manzini & Thorpe, 2018).

As for people, we consider that participatory design, by definition, involves in a common practice people of different ages, cultures, types of knowledge, skills and interests. They bring into the discussion a variety of perspectives, which, both enrich and problematise any conversation. *Design in the Middle*, although introduced as a transdisciplinary work, gathered a selected group of 30 designers and architects. According to records, the list of participants was very diverse, as regards provenance, age and experience. The composition of the team, though, was far different from usual, for participants shared a common education and professional background. This condition does not necessarily encourage meaningful encounters: we all know how tough a conversation among peers – particularly designers – can be, each one defending his/her culture, experience and beliefs. However, this distinction from usual practice might have contributed to successful results. Author(s)’ guideline *Embracing diversity* is partially confirmed by the analysis of the case study, for it stresses the importance of differences, albeit on the basis of a shared background.

In respect of activities, our previous studies focused on strategies enhancing interpersonal exchange rather than on methods applied in addressing issues at stake. Distinctive aspects of the design process, such as the shaping of the brief or the identification of goals to achieve, exceeded the perimeter of our research. Significantly, the scheduling of *Design in the middle* activities confirms our recommendation to balance workload between focused activity and open, informal conversations (*Never mind the clock*) conveying “the feeling that within that context time rules are different from the ordinary” (Devecchi, 2018, p.155).

At the same time, the workshop crafts the design process in ways that can boost empathic experience. In particular, we refer to low-detailed design briefs and to the “open” titles given to them. These two tactics no doubt not only stimulated imagination and speculative thinking, but also encouraged the free exploration of ideas and suggestions by whoever had them, thus promoting peer-to-peer conversation and cooperation. Even fixing the time horizon in three years (2020) might have contributed to success as it provided participants with a kind of “conceptual” risk-free zone, out of the constraints that current conditions impose for elaborating reliable solutions. In this respect, shaping the contents of collaborative design practices precisely to enable empathic experience seems to be a promising field of future investigation.

Boella argues that it is time to open up new horizons in empathy-related studies, in which empathy is not an idealised object of speculation. Rather, she suggests, understanding empathy requires a practical perspective, focused on “historical, cultural and social situations in which tuning into others’ differences is difficult or rejected” (Boella, 2018b, p.10). Similarly, both the CoR project and Wilson and Arvanitakis’ study (2013) focus on practices of resilience, i.e. activities that allow communities to weave a resilient social fabric, suitable for facing crisis and responding appropriately. From this perspective, we can argue that by enabling collaborative activities we provide opportunities for *empathy in practice*. “Empathy is crucial to fostering meaningful encounters between people” (Manzini & Thorpe, 2018, p.7), and communities are built on meaningful encounters. If we acknowledge that resilience requires “engagement in processes” (Arvanitakis, 2014, p.66) involving people within communities, and that enabling empathic experiences can strengthen cooperation among individuals, the development of tools geared to that becomes crucial. In this respect, this essay might have taken a step forward on a broader research path about how to capitalise on human relationships towards more resilient cultures and societies.

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